

The Science of the Seasons - Spatial Analysis of Phenological Data

Chris Brunsdon*¹

¹National Centre for Geocomputation, Maynooth University, Iontas Building, W23 F2H6
Maynooth, Ireland

GISRUK 2026

Summary

This talk frames phenology - the study of how the timing of seasons shifts across time - as a spatial data problem as much as an ecological one. It examines how seasonal biological timing responds to climate change using spatially explicit data from a citizen observation network, The USA National Phenology Network, based on first flowering dates of the common lilac (*Syringa Vulgaris*). The emphasis is on scale, spatial heterogeneity, and uncertainty, highlighting methods such as spatial smoothing, geographically varying relationships, and temporal trend modelling. By treating phenology as a geographically structured process, the talk shows how spatial analysis strengthens inference on changing climate impacts across geographical space.

KEYWORDS: Phenology, Climate Variability, Spatial Modelling, Nonparametric Modelling, Temporal Trends

1 Introduction and Motivation

Phenology is the study of the timing of recurring biological events—such as flowering, leaf emergence, or bird migration—and how these timings vary across time and space in response to environmental conditions. Because phenological events are tightly coupled to temperature and other climatic drivers, they are among the most sensitive and consistently observed biological indicators of climate change (Menzel et al., 2006; Parmesan & Yohe, 2003). Across many temperate regions, long-term records show a systematic advance of spring events and, in some cases, delayed autumn transitions, providing clear empirical evidence of a warming climate (Cleland et al., 2007).

While phenology is often framed as an ecological process, it is fundamentally a spatial one. Phenological responses vary geographically due to differences in local climate, topography, land cover, and observation density, leading to strong spatial heterogeneity and non-stationarity in climate–phenology relationships. Analyses based on spatially aggregated trends risk obscuring this variation and misrepresenting local climate impacts. This work positions phenology explicitly within

*christopher.brunsdon@mu.ie

GIScience, treating phenological observations as spatial data that require geographically aware analytical methods. By adopting spatial statistical and modelling approaches, phenology can be used more effectively to quantify, visualise, and interpret climate change impacts across geographical space.

2 Data and Study Context

The analysis draws on phenological observations collected through citizen science, focusing on first flowering dates as a biologically meaningful and climatically sensitive indicator of seasonal change. In particular, the study uses data from the USA National Phenology Network (USA-NPN) (Weltzin et al., 2020), which coordinates large-scale, standardised recording of phenological events across the United States. The USA-NPN provides spatially extensive, openly available observations contributed by trained volunteers and practitioners, making it a key resource for spatial phenology research (Schwartz & Reiter, 2000; Schwartz et al., 2012).

The focal phenophase examined here is the first flowering date of the common lilac (*Syringa vulgaris*), recorded as the number of days since January 1st. this species is widely used in phenological studies due to its broad geographic distribution, ease of identification, and well-documented sensitivity to spring temperature (Schwartz & Reiter, 2000). Locations of the observed plants are given in Figure 1. Lilac flowering has a long history as a phenological indicator in North America, allowing contemporary citizen observations to be interpreted in the context of earlier monitoring efforts.

Figure 1: Locations of Lilac Plants.

Spatially, the dataset spans a wide range of climatic regions across the contiguous United States, while temporally it covers multiple decades of observations, though with uneven density over time. From a GIScience perspective, the primary strengths of the data lie in its geographic coverage and temporal resolution. However, limitations include spatial clustering of observations, variable observer effort, and missing data, all of which necessitate careful spatial modelling and uncertainty-aware analysis. Figure 2 suggests uneven temporal distribution of observations, with fewer observations after 1990.

Figure 2: Number of observations in each year.

2.1 Phenology, Climate, and Geography

Phenological timing is closely linked to climatic conditions, particularly temperature, making point-based phenological observations a direct and sensitive record of local climate variability and change. Spring events such as first flowering are commonly associated with accumulated thermal forcing, and their timing reflects the climatic conditions experienced at specific locations rather than area-averaged environments (Chuine & Régnière, 2017). This point-level nature of phenological data distinguishes it from many ecological datasets and aligns naturally with spatial analytical approaches.

Although observations are recorded at discrete locations—often tied to individual, repeatedly observed plants—the climatic drivers influencing these events operate across multiple spatial scales. Local phenological responses may be shaped by fine-scale variation in elevation, land cover, or microclimate, even where regional climate trends are broadly similar. As a result, identical climatic anomalies can produce heterogeneous phenological responses across space, due to genuine geographic variation in climate sensitivity (Wolkovich et al., 2012).

From a GIScience viewpoint, treating phenology as a geographically structured point process allows spatial heterogeneity and non-stationarity in climate–phenology relationships to be explicitly examined. This motivates analytical approaches that estimate locally varying relationships while preserving the integrity of point-based observations, enabling more accurate spatial inference on how climate change affects seasonal timing across space.

3 Underlying Statistical Model

The key task here is to model geographically referenced first bloom data using Equation 1

$$y = S_j + f(t) + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

where y is the first bloom day, S_j is the effect associated with observation station j and $f(t)$ is a function of time t . Estimates for S_j are shown in Figure 3. Equation 1 has a quite general form - essentially it is the sum of a time trend - giving the change in first flowering date, and a geographical effect linked to then location of the observation of the flowering. The former is a continuous function of time, the latter a random vector of baseline first flowering days, as a random m -element vector. The list of possible choices for multivariate vector distributions and potential functions of time is very broad. In future alternatives will be considered but initially, $\{S_j\}$ will be modelled as a multivariate Gaussian distribution. In an earlier study (Brunsdon & Comber, 2012) examined the use of a linear $f(t)$ which was found to have a negative slope. Also (Nummer & Song, 2020) fit a ‘hockey stick’ model with a change point from one (flat) linear $f(t)$ to another. Here $f(t)$ will be chosen to be a continuous monotone decreasing function based on a cubic spline-based function. This widens the space of the kinds of $f(t)$ to be explored. The estimates of the specific values of S_j and f are obtained by analysing the NPN data. Here, the possibility of an arbitrary but decreasing $f(t)$ is explored. This basic constraint is expressed in Equation 2.

$$f'(t) \leq 0 \quad \forall t \quad (2)$$

In contrast to the two-stage linear model, this allows other changes in advance rate to occur during the study period.

In computational terms the (*Shape Constrained Additive Models*) `scam` library in R (Pya & Wood, 2016) is used to fit these models.

3.1 Space Time Interaction

The approach outline here is additive, so that the changes in first bloom date are a geographical effect superimposed on a time trend. This is a relatively simple model that offers ease of interpretation with a fair overview of the process. However, it is possible that greater insight may be gained if space-time interaction is considered. This allows for complexity not captured in an additive model, where the time trends may vary geographically. In a very basic consideration of this issue, the NPN data is split into three broad zones geographically (*East*, *Mid* and *West*) and estimates of $f(t)$ for each individual subset are viewed, to see the extent of the variability.

4 Results

Looking at spatial trends in the first bloom date - the S_t part of the model - there is a strong latitudinal trend with a secondary coastal–continental pattern. Stations in the northern US tend to have later first bloom dates (blue), while southern stations—especially across the Southwest and southern California—show earlier dates (red). This suggests a latitude/temperature control. The

western US shows the strongest contrast: early dates in the southwest, flipping to later dates in the Pacific Northwest and northern Rockies.

Figure 3: Station Effects for first flower days.

In temporal terms ($f(t)$), this shows a clear, accelerating temporal trend toward earlier first bloom dates (Figure 4). The trend is not linear. There is a relatively gentle decline from the 1950s through the 1970s, followed by a steeper slope from later. The confidence band widens toward the end of the series, reflecting greater uncertainty in recent (post 1990) years, likely due to fewer observations.

Figure 5 shows the regional comparisons. This visualises the different $f(t)$ curves for regions within the US. Due to the lower numbers of observations after 1990, the graphs focus on the period prior to this date. The figure shows estimated time trends in first flowering date (on the linear predictor scale) from 1970 to 1990 for three broad U.S. regions: East, Central, and West. All regions exhibit a declining trend over time, indicating progressively earlier flowering dates. The East starts with the latest fitted dates in 1970 and shows a steady forward trend. The Central region follows a similar but slightly weaker trend. The West displays the most rapid advance, with fitted values advancing more rapidly after around 1980 and ending substantially earlier than the other regions by 1990.

5 Conclusion

Taken together, these results reinforce the view that phenology is not merely a temporal signal of climate change but a fundamentally spatial one. Advances in flowering dates are widespread, yet their magnitude and trajectory vary markedly across geographical space, reflecting heterogeneous climate sensitivities and regional contexts. By framing phenological change through spatially explicit, constraint-aware models, this work demonstrates how GIScience methods can sharpen inference, reveal hidden structure, and better communicate uncertainty in climate impacts. As citizen-science phenology networks continue to grow, spatial analysis will be essential—not only for documenting change, but for understanding where, how, and how fast seasonal systems are responding to a warming world.

Figure 4: Time trend for first flower day

Figure 5: Time Trends for first flower days by region.

Acknowledgements

This work makes use of phenological observation data provided by the USA National Phenology Network (USA-NPN). We gratefully acknowledge the many volunteer observers and contributing organisations whose efforts make these data available, as well as the USA-NPN staff for coordinating data collection, quality control, and open access to the data set.

Biographies

Chris Brunsdon is Professor of Geocomputation at Maynooth University's National Centre for Geocomputation. His research focuses on spatial statistics, geographically weighted methods, and the analysis of spatial heterogeneity, with applications spanning environmental change, socio-spatial inequality, and spatial data science.

References

- Brunsdon, C., & Comber, A. (2012). Assessing the changing flowering date of the common lilac in north america: A random coefficient model approach. *GeoInformatica*, *16*(4), 675–690. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10707-012-0159-6>
- Chuine, I., & Régnière, J. (2017). Process-based models of phenology for plants and animals. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, *48*, 159–182. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-110316-022706>
- Cleland, E. E., Chuine, I., Menzel, A., Mooney, H. A., & Schwartz, M. D. (2007). Shifting plant phenology in response to global change. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, *22*(7), 357–365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2007.04.003>
- Menzel, A., Sparks, T. H., Estrella, N., Koch, E., Aasa, A., Ahas, R., Alm-Kübler, K., et al. (2006). European phenological response to climate change matches the warming pattern. *Global Change Biology*, *12*(10), 1969–1976. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2006.01193.x>
- Nummer, S. A., & Song, S. Q. (2020). A hierarchical threshold modeling approach for understanding phenological responses to climate change: When did north american lilacs start to bloom earlier? *SN Applied Sciences*, *2*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-03847-z>
- Parmesan, C., & Yohe, G. (2003). A globally coherent fingerprint of climate change impacts across natural systems. *Nature*, *421*(6918), 37–42. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature01286>
- Pyra, N., & Wood, S. (2016). Shape constrained additive models. *Statistics and Computing*, *25*(3), 543–559. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.package.scam>
- Schwartz, M. D., Betancourt, J. L., & Weltzin, J. F. (2012). Phenology: An integrative environmental science. *Ecological Monographs*, *82*(3), 329–352. <https://doi.org/10.1890/11-1691.1>
- Schwartz, M. D., & Reiter, B. E. (2000). Changes in north american spring. *International Journal of Climatology*, *20*(8), 929–932. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-0088\(20000630\)20:8<929::AID-JOC557>3.0.CO;2-5](https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-0088(20000630)20:8<929::AID-JOC557>3.0.CO;2-5)

- Weltzin, J. F., Betancourt, J. L., Cook, B. I., Crimmins, T. M., Enquist, C. A. F., Gerst, K. L., Gross, J. E., et al. (2020). Biological life cycle events and climate change: A usa national phenology network perspective. *Ecological Monographs*, *90*(4), e01406. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecm.1406>
- Wolkovich, E. M., Cook, B. I., Allen, J. M., Crimmins, T. M., Betancourt, J. L., Travers, S. E., Pau, S., et al. (2012). Warming experiments underpredict plant phenological responses to climate change. *Nature*, *485*(7399), 494–497. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11014>